
SOME THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS OF THE PROBLEM OF COGNITIVE ACTIVITY OF STUDENTS

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Abstract.

Cognitive activity is a condition for the formation of students' need for knowledge, mastering the skills of intellectual activity, independence, ensuring the depth and strength of knowledge. The article deals with the current state of the problem of formation cognitive activity of students and the main components and indicators of the formation of levels of cognitive activity.

Keywords.

cognitive activity, personal education, educational process, interest.

Introduction.

Modern society sets the goal of educational institutions of various types not only to gain knowledge, to form skills and abilities, but also to develop the cognitive activity of students.

The activity to transform Uzbekistan educational institutions into a self-regulatory system, among other things, encounters difficulties associated with the very poor preparedness of the vast majority of students for learning in the new conditions. This position determined the huge demand for a new type of student - an active and independent student.

Literature review:

The problem of the development of cognitive activity is one of the priority tasks in pedagogy. The problem of cognitive activity is considered in the works of L.S. Vygotsky, A.N. Leontiev, G.I. Schukina K.D. Ushinsky, etc.

Cognitive activity is a valuable and complex personal education of a student. Its manifestations in each subsequent age are wider, richer; they have an impact on the productivity of learning and teaching, on the activation of all educational activities. The value of a lesson is most often determined through the activity of

students. Cognitive activity can be considered a preparatory stage of independence [1, 174].

Educational and cognitive competence - the student's readiness for independent cognitive activity: goal-setting, planning, analysis, reflection, self-assessment of educational and cognitive activity, the ability to distinguish facts from conjectures, possession of measurement skills, the use of probabilistic, statistical and other methods of cognition. The independence of students consists of self-education, self-analysis, self-learning, self-control, self-observation, self-discipline, self-esteem. The entire educational process depends on cognitive interest, which is the most important stimulus for any activity of students. The productivity of knowledge assimilation also depends on interest. Therefore, the problem arose of how to activate the cognitive activity of students, how to make the learning process "education with passion" for all students.

Cognitive activity and independence - a recognized means of increasing the consciousness and effectiveness of the student, the result of the effective organization of the educational process, an integral part of mental development, which determines the degree of its formation; this is mentioned in the works of M.A. Danilova, I.Ya. Lerner, M.R. Lvov, A.Ya.Savchenko, G.A.Tsukerman and others.

Discussion.

As these studies show, active learning activities of foreign language learners are necessary at various stages of mastering the material.

The use of various forms, methods and means of training: scientific and creative work, group work, pair work, project technology, gamification, modular, role-playing games, discussions, ICT contributes to the formation and further development of communicative competencies, independence; development of skills to work in cooperation, form, express and defend one's position, take a different point of view, develop cognitive interest, tolerance, skills are formed to practice not only mutual control, mutual assessment, but also self-control, self-respect [28,912].

Cognitive activity as a quality of personality develops in students and in the course of dialogues and discussions in the study of various disciplines. Pluralism of opinions, the expansion of publicity may raise the importance of the ability to argue, the culture of discussions to a new height. At seminars, in the course of independent work, during discussions, both planned and spontaneously arising, during round tables, press conferences, discussion clubs, teachers help students

overcome difficulties in proving their point of view, in selecting arguments in favor of the correctness of their statements, in compliance with the rules of controversy.

When studying the features of the functioning of cognitive activity, the following are noted:

- The level of development of attention, memory, imagination;
- Success in overcoming cognitive difficulties;
- the frequency of speeches in the lesson and posing questions to the teacher; - development of skills of independent knowledge; - the ability to highlight the main thing, to prove, to express knowledge; - participation in scientific work;
- Helping fellow students.

Cognitive activity in its specific manifestation is purely individual in nature. The effective development of creative cognitive activity of students in the classroom in the academic disciplines of a foreign language is ensured by their joint activities with the teacher during the educational process due to the purposeful development of motives for active learning among students, creative cooperation between teachers and students in the classroom, the widespread introduction of dialogue and discussion in the process of conducting classes, the individualization of work on the development of cognitive activity [43,13]. Determining the features of students' cognitive activity is carried out by the teacher in the process of conversation, during the observation in the lesson using a detailed assessment of cognitive activity.

Training should involve the creation of conditions for the development of cognitive activity, because it is a manifestation of specific personal characteristics that are realized in behavior as a special form of activity aimed at searching and discovering something new, as a characteristic of an object and integrating new information into the content of personal experience [13, 299].

Cognitive activity is formed as an aspect of cognitive activity, and as a property of a person, it is strengthened and developed as a result of a specially organized cognitive process. In addition, it is proposed to consider the following recommendations for the development of cognitive activity of students in the educational process of technical universities:

- An increase in cognitive activity should be considered as a search for the foundations for the unity of the content and methodological aspects of education, the structure of which ensures high cognitive activity and cognitive interest among students;

- As a psychological basis for the development of cognitive activity of students is the presence of their cognitive interest in the content of education, both in terms of its subject content, and in terms of forms and methods of teaching. [42, 279] Thus, the activation of cognitive activity is a complex process that includes a number of interrelated activities.

Conclusion:

Hence, the main directions of enhancing the cognitive activity of students can be summarized in three groups.

The first group: the formation of students' motives and needs for learning, mastering knowledge, skills and abilities in their future specialty; the formation of trainees' techniques, skills and abilities of educational work.

The second group: ensuring the unity of the educational, developing and nurturing tasks of the learning process; improving the forms and methods of teaching students; pedagogically correct use by teachers of the principles of didactics in educational work; improving the efficiency and ensuring the regularity of monitoring and assessing knowledge of skills and abilities; rational organization of practical training of trainees.

Third group: involvement of trainees in active participation in extracurricular activities; development and proper use of a system of pedagogical and psychological incentives for the educational activities of students; establishing close interdisciplinary links in teaching; continuous improvement of pedagogical skills of teachers.

The implementation of these areas in practice will improve the quality of students' knowledge, equip them with methods of a scientific approach to the analysis of various phenomena and processes, and develop the necessary professional qualities in them.

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